

CLINICAL MANAGEMENT OF PERIPHERAL OSSIFYING FIBROMA- A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is a reactive gingival lesion arising in response to chronic irritation or trauma. This report describes a case of POF in a 31-year-old female who presented with a four-month history of a slowly enlarging, painless swelling in the posterior maxillary gingiva in the region of tooth #26. Clinical examination revealed a firm, pedunculated growth measuring approximately 1 cm × 1 cm with no ulceration. Radiographic evaluation revealed faint radiopacities within the soft tissue lesion. Surgical excision was performed under local anesthesia using a crevicular incision from the mid-buccal of tooth #25 to the mid-buccal of tooth #27, followed by flap reflection, thorough debridement and curettage, and complete excision of the swelling. Histopathological evaluation confirmed the diagnosis of POF, revealing a cellular fibroblastic stroma with mineralized foci. Postoperative healing was uneventful, and the patient remains under follow-up with no signs of recurrence. This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis and complete surgical excision in the management of POF to prevent recurrence.

KEYWORDS

Peripheral Ossifying Fibroma, Reactive Gingival Lesion, Excisional Biopsy, Oral Pathology, Case Report

INTRODUCTION.

Localized gingival overgrowths are a common finding in clinical dental practice. These growths represent a diverse group of reactive lesions that arise in response to persistent local irritation or trauma, often due to plaque, calculus, overhanging restorations, or other mechanical factors. Although these lesions are generally benign, their clinical presentation can be striking, and they may mimic neoplastic processes, thereby warranting careful examination and histopathological evaluation to establish a definitive diagnosis.^{1,2}

Among these reactive lesions, peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is recognized as a relatively common entity. POF accounts for approximately 9% of all gingival lesions and typically presents as a slow-growing, firm, nodular mass. This lesion most commonly affects adolescents and young adults, with a predilection for females, and tends to occur more frequently in the anterior maxillary region^{3,4}. The lesion may remain asymptomatic for a considerable period, although it can cause discomfort, impede oral hygiene, and lead to aesthetic concerns if it enlarges significantly.

The etiology and pathogenesis of POF are still not completely understood. However, it is widely accepted that POF arises from the cells of the periodontal ligament, which possess the capacity for osteogenic and cementogenic differentiation. Local irritants, such as dental plaque, calculus, and trauma from dental appliances, are thought to contribute to its reactive proliferation.⁵ The mineralized material observed within the lesion is believed to result from metaplastic changes within the connective tissue or from the maturation of fibrous tissue in response to chronic inflammation.

Histopathological examination is crucial for establishing a definitive diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma, as its clinical features may overlap with other gingival lesions. Microscopically, POF is characterized by a highly cellular fibroblastic stroma composed of plump fibroblasts and spindle-shaped cells embedded in a collagenous matrix. This fibrous connective tissue stroma may exhibit varying degrees of vascularity, with some

areas appearing more collagenous and others showing a myxoid or loose arrangement.⁶ A hallmark feature of POF is the presence of mineralized material within the lesion. This mineralized component typically includes: Bone trabeculae, Cementum-like deposits (These basophilic, acellular structures are sometimes described as resembling cementicles) Dystrophic calcifications. The overlying epithelium is generally stratified squamous in nature and may be intact or exhibit ulceration, particularly in lesions subjected to trauma. In ulcerated areas, a fibrinopurulent membrane with acute inflammatory cell infiltration is often seen.⁷

The mineralized components are thought to arise from metaplastic transformation of the connective tissue due to chronic irritation, leading to the deposition of bone or cementum-like material.¹ The pattern and proportion of these mineralized materials can vary widely, giving rise to a spectrum of histological appearances.

Several attempts have been made to classify gingival localized overgrowths based on clinical and histopathological features. One of the widely cited approaches includes grouping them into four main types:- Pyogenic granuloma, Peripheral giant cell granuloma, Peripheral ossifying fibroma, Fibroma (irritation fibroma)^{1,2}

Understanding this classification is essential for accurate diagnosis and management, as each lesion type differs in histogenesis, treatment approaches, and recurrence potential. Among these, POF is particularly notable for its tendency to recur if the lesion is not excised completely or if local etiological factors persist. Recurrence rates for POF have been reported to range from 8% to 20%⁷, highlighting the need for meticulous surgical removal and ongoing follow-up care.

Radiographically, peripheral ossifying fibroma is often a soft tissue lesion and may not always show definitive radiographic changes. However, in some cases, particularly when there is a significant amount of mineralization within the lesion, radiographic features can be observed. Soft tissue shadow or opacity, Superficial bone involvement, No significant bone destruction- Unlike central ossifying fibromas or aggressive giant cell lesions, POF does not typically cause significant bone expansion, destruction, or displacement of adjacent teeth.⁸

Differential Considerations

The radiographic appearance of POF may overlap with other soft tissue calcifying lesions such as peripheral giant cell granuloma (which can cause superficial bone resorption) and fibrous epulis. The key distinguishing feature is the presence of mineralized foci within the soft tissue, which, in the appropriate clinical context, strongly suggests POF.

Given its clinical significance and the necessity for precise diagnosis, this case report aims to present a detailed account of a peripheral ossifying fibroma in a young female patient. The report discusses the clinical presentation, radiographic features, histopathological findings, and the comprehensive management plan employed to ensure optimal treatment outcomes. Through this case, we underscore the importance of distinguishing POF from other gingival overgrowths and emphasize the role of thorough excision and regular follow-up to prevent recurrence.⁵

METHOD AND MATERIAL

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 31-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Periodontology at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital with a chief complaint of a swelling in the upper posterior gingiva that had been present for approximately four months. The patient first noticed a small, painless growth in the interdental region between her upper first molar region. Initially, the lesion was no larger than a small pea and did not cause any significant discomfort. Over the subsequent months, however, the swelling gradually increased in size, becoming more prominent and noticeable during routine oral hygiene practices.

The patient reported mild discomfort while chewing and brushing in the affected area, but she did not experience any spontaneous pain or bleeding. She noted that the swelling occasionally bled when subjected to trauma during brushing or eating hard foods. Patient was having history of ongoing orthodontic treatment since 8-9 months but she denied any systemic illnesses or relevant medical history. There was no history of pregnancy.

The patient did not report any specific factors that aggravated or relieved the swelling. She mentioned that although the swelling seemed to remain relatively stable in size for a few months, it had recently shown a slight increase in bulk, prompting her to seek professional evaluation.

On extraoral examination, there was no facial asymmetry or lymphadenopathy. Intraoral examination revealed a single, well-circumscribed, nodular growth located on the attached gingiva in region of 26. The lesion measured approximately 1 cm × 1 cm, was pinkish-red in color, and had a firm, rubbery consistency. The surface appeared smooth to irregular, with no signs of ulceration or necrosis. The swelling was pedunculated, non-fluctuant, and non-tender on palpation, although the patient reported mild sensitivity when pressure was applied.

Oral hygiene was fair, with mild plaque accumulation in the area surrounding the lesion. patient was unable to brush properly due to presence of orthodontic braces. No significant tooth mobility or displacement was noted in the adjacent teeth. Radiographic examination using an intraoral periapical radiograph did not reveal any remarkable bone changes, although faint radiopacities within the soft tissue shadow suggested the presence of calcifications.

Based on the clinical presentation and history (Figure 1A,1B), a provisional diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma was made, with differential diagnosis of pyogenic granuloma, traumatic fibroma, peripheral giant cell granuloma.

Figure 1A,1B - Preoperative Clinical presentation of the lesion

An excisional biopsy was planned to obtain a definitive diagnosis and to eliminate the lesion. After obtaining informed consent, the patient was prepared for surgical excision of the lesion under local anesthesia. Local infiltration anesthesia was achieved using 2% lidocaine with 1:80,000 epinephrine to ensure profound anesthesia and hemostasis. To accurately locate the base of the swelling, a sterile suture thread was gently passed around the lesion and used as a marker, allowing precise delineation of the lesion's origin and attachment to the gingival tissues (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Base of lesion located

A crevicular incision was then made using a No. 15 blade, extending from the mid-buccal aspect of tooth #25 to the mid-buccal aspect of tooth #27. Care was taken to maintain the incision within the attached gingiva and to preserve as much healthy tissue as possible. Vertical releasing incisions were not deemed necessary due to the limited extent of the lesion. A full-thickness mucoperiosteal flap was gently reflected using a periosteal elevator to provide access and adequate visibility of the lesion and underlying structures (fig 3A). Once the lesion was fully exposed, meticulous debridement and curettage of the adjacent periodontal tissues and underlying periosteum were performed to remove any residual granulation tissue and to ensure complete excision of the lesion's base (fig 3B). The entire lesion was excised in toto with a scalpel (fig 3C), ensuring that the excision extended slightly beyond the clinically visible margins to minimize the risk of recurrence.

Figure 3A,3B,3C – Reflection of flap and Excision of the lesion.

Hemostasis was achieved with pressure and suction. Following excision, the surgical site was thoroughly irrigated with sterile saline to remove any residual debris. The flap was then carefully repositioned and approximated to its original position using interrupted 3-0 black silk sutures to ensure proper tissue adaptation and promote optimal healing (fig 4A). A periodontal dressing (Coe-Pak) was placed over the surgical area to protect the site and to provide additional comfort and stability during the initial healing phase (fig 4B).

Figure 4A ,4B – Suturing and placement of periodontal pack

The patient was given postoperative instructions regarding oral hygiene, dietary modifications, and the use of prescribed analgesics and antimicrobial mouth rinses. She was advised to avoid trauma to the area and was scheduled for follow-up visits to monitor healing and to remove the sutures after one week (fig 5)

Figure 5 – follow up after 7 days.

Microscopic Examination: The given H&E-Stained tissue section reveals a fibro-cellular tissue lined by stratified squamous parakeratinized epithelium. The epithelium is intact throughout the studied section. The underlying connective tissue shows dense collagen fibers with infiltration of numerous chronic inflammatory cells chiefly consisting of lymphocytes and few plasma cells. The deeper stroma shows bony trabeculae containing osteocytes within the lacunae which are intermixed with basophilic masses of cementum-like tissue of variable sizes and shapes.

Figure 6 - H&E- Stained tissue section of the lesion

Discussion

Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is a relatively common, reactive gingival lesion that typically presents as a firm, localized mass. It is considered to originate from the periodontal ligament or periosteum in response to chronic local irritation, such as plaque, calculus, or dental appliances⁹. In the present case, a 31-year-old female patient presented with a slowly enlarging, painless gingival swelling in the posterior maxilla, a common site for POF.¹⁰

The classic presentation of POF is a well-demarcated, sessile or pedunculated growth with a smooth or occasionally ulcerated surface. The female predilection observed in the present case aligns with earlier studies suggesting hormonal influences, particularly in women of reproductive age.¹¹ The lesion in this case had been present for approximately four months, exhibiting a slow, progressive growth pattern, which is typical of POF and helps distinguish it from more aggressive gingival pathologies.

Histologically, POF is characterized by a highly cellular fibroblastic stroma intermixed with mineralized material in the form of bone, cementum-like structures, or dystrophic calcifications.¹² These mineralized foci are believed to arise from metaplastic transformation of connective tissue in response to chronic irritation.¹³ In the present case, histopathological examination confirmed the presence of cellular fibrous tissue with mineralized components, thus supporting the clinical diagnosis.

Radiographically, POF generally does not involve the underlying alveolar bone, although mineralized foci within the soft tissue may appear as faint radiopacities.⁵ In this case, intraoral periapical radiographs revealed faint radiopacities within the soft tissue shadow of the lesion, consistent with the mineralized deposits commonly associated with POF.

Surgical excision, including the removal of the lesion's base and thorough curettage of the underlying periodontal ligament, is the treatment of choice to reduce the risk of recurrence.¹⁴ In this case, the lesion was excised completely through a crevicular incision with careful flap reflection, debridement, and curettage. Postoperative healing was uneventful, and the patient was advised to maintain meticulous oral hygiene and return for regular follow-up.

Recurrence rates for POF have been reported to range from 8% to 20%.⁹ Recurrence is often attributed to incomplete excision or failure to remove local irritants. Therefore, elimination of contributing factors, such as plaque and calculus, and meticulous surgical technique are essential in preventing recurrence^{9,10}.

In summary, this case underscores the importance of considering POF in the differential diagnosis of gingival overgrowths, particularly in young females presenting with a firm, localized gingival mass. Early diagnosis, appropriate surgical excision, and elimination of etiological factors are critical to ensuring successful management and minimizing the risk of recurrence.

CONCLUSION

Peripheral Ossifying Fibroma is a reactive gingival lesion that necessitates accurate clinical diagnosis and prompt surgical management to prevent recurrence. In this case, excisional biopsy proved both diagnostic and therapeutic, with successful healing and no signs of recurrence during follow-up. This emphasizes the importance of complete lesion removal along with underlying tissue curettage and consistent post-operative monitoring in ensuring favorable outcomes.

REFERENCES.

1. Kfir Y, Buchner A, Hansen LS. Reactive lesions of the gingiva: a clinicopathological study of 741 cases. *J Periodontol.* 1980;51(11):655-661.
2. Katsikeris N, Kakarantza-Angelopoulou E, Angelopoulos AP. Peripheral ossifying fibroma: a clinicopathologic study of 14 cases. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 1987;45(10):879-884.
3. Farquhar T, MacLellan J, Dymment H, Anderson RD. Peripheral ossifying fibroma: a case report. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 2008;74(9):809-812.
4. Kumar SKS, Ram S, Jorgensen MG, Shuler CF, Sedghizadeh PP. Multicentric peripheral ossifying fibroma: a case report and review of the literature. *J Oral Sci.* 2013;55(3):327-332.
5. Eversole LR, Rovin S. Reactive lesions of the gingiva. *J Oral Pathol.* 1972;1(1):30-38
6. Buchner A, Hansen LS. The histomorphologic spectrum of peripheral ossifying fibroma. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1987;63(4):452-461.
7. Neville BW, Damm DD, Allen CM, Chi AC. *Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology.* 4th ed. St. Louis, MO: Elsevier; 2016.
8. Collins LH, Zegalie NF, Sassoon I, Speight PM. A clinical, radiological and histopathological review of 74 ossifying fibromas. *Head and Neck Pathology.* 2023 Jun;17(2):433-46.
9. Cundiff EJ. Peripheral ossifying fibroma: A review of 365 cases. Indiana University Libraries; 1972.
10. Kenney JN, Kaugars GE, Abbey LM. Comparison between the peripheral ossifying fibroma and peripheral odontogenic fibroma. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 1989;47(4): 378-382.
11. Sammons ML, Wysocki GP. Histogenesis of peripheral ossifying fibroma. *J Oral Pathol.* 1981;10(4): 201-209.
12. Kurtz M, Mesa M, Holt GR. Peripheral ossifying fibroma: a clinical and radiographic study. *J Oral Med.* 1987;42(3): 97-100.
13. Gardner DG. The peripheral odontogenic fibroma: an attempt at clarification. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1982;54(1): 40-48.
14. Marino MJ, Sanz M, Herrera D. Surgical approach for the management of peripheral ossifying fibroma: a report of three cases. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2005;32(5): 515-519.